

Design of artificial chloroform Bulk Liquid Membrane (BLM) filled with supramolecular receptors and its application in selective transport of valine and leucine amino acids.

Jyoti Tomar¹, Praval Chauhan²

¹Department of Chemistry, School of Sciences, ² Department of Paramedical Sciences

ITM (SLS) Baroda University, Dhanora Tank Road, Off Halol Highway, Near Jarod, Paldi, Vadodara, Gujarat India

Graphical Abstract

Figure 1.: Bulk Liquid Membrane prototype ; transport behaviour of solute and solvents in feed as well as in permeate and the membrane phase.

Abstract: A new series of receptors were designed and synthesised by the reported methods and characterised by melting point, TLC, elemental analysis, IR, ¹HNMR, C¹³NMR, and LCMS Mass spectrometry. These synthetic supramolecular receptors were used as carrier for transport of various amino acids (Glycine, Valine, Leucine, and Proline through chloroform bulk liquid membrane system. Liquid-liquid extraction studies were performed to understand the stability of receptor- amino acid complex. The basic fundamental parameters including amino acid concentration, effect of solvent, pH of the feed/source phase, acid, base and salt concentration in the strip/receiving solution, receptor concentration in the membrane phase, rate of stirring and effect of time was studied.

The optimum concentration of amino acid for transport is 1×10^{-1} M and for receptor is 1×10^{-4} M. Transport of amino acid was not affected by the presence of salts such as sodium chloride and sodium sulphates in feed solution.

The observed trend for the extraction of amino acids by these receptors is valin>leucine>glycine (Table 1). The results reveals that receptor J₁& J₂ both extract valine at greater extant while release/transport less (table 2). Structure of receptor affected the extraction and transport phenomena. Receptors J₁, J₂ possess (Scheme1) tri and diethylene glycol chain length and rigid azo naphthyl end groups. Therefore It is suggested that these receptors (J₁-J₂) interact with amino acids by hydrogen bonding between -NH₄⁺ moiety of amino acid and donor

oxygen sites of the receptor. The extraction of amino acids observed also follow the sequence of hydrophobicity scale i.e. valine > Leucine > glycine.

No detectable amount of Extraction and transport of amino acids were not observed by Receptor J₃ and J₄. Those are used as such as receptor. Molecular tailoring/designing of receptor is fruitful for better selectiveness.

The receptors (J₅ and J₆) are better carrier for valine and leucine amino acids due to weak interactions of naphthyl side arm with amino acid. Selective transport of valine and leucine is observed and the percentage of valine and leucine transported through receptor bearing chloroform liquid membrane after 24 Hours was $88 \pm 0.1\%$ and $69 \pm 0.1\%$ respectively.

Keywords: Supramolecular Receptors, Bulk liquid membrane (BLM), Feed phase, Stripping phase, selectivity, transport

. Introduction

Liquid membrane (LM) has been given considerable attention by the researchers for removal and recovery of heavy metals from aqueous solutions. Some of the pronounced advantages of LM over the traditional separation methods are: low capital and operating costs, low energy and solvent consumption, high concentration factors, and high fluxes [1]. The membrane separation techniques, namely, microfiltration, ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, electro-dialysis, and so forth, are being used in the industrial scale for separation of different components from solutions [2-8]. In all the membrane separation process, membrane used is basically a thin film and porous in nature, which acts as a semipermeable barrier for allowing certain component to transport and others to reject. Depending on the feed and the process the product may be permeated or may be rejected by the membrane.

In recent years these membrane separation processes are paid considerable attention because of their energy efficiency. Such a typical process membrane separation process with the transport behaviour of solute and solvents in feed as well as in permeate and the membrane phase is shown in **Figure 1**.

This reactive liquid membrane system has emerged as a novel and effective tool in separation technique and display high selectivity due to specific interaction with guest molecules by the carrier which facilitates the separation through membranes. [9,10]

Supramolecular receptors like crown ethers [11] podands [12], lariat ethers [13] and calixarenes [14] have found applications for the selective transport of ions and biomolecules through bulk and supported liquid membrane systems. [15,16].

Ma et al. [17] reported the transport of amino acid through di-(2-ethylhexyl) phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) as carrier in kerosene. The liquid membrane system exhibited excellent transport selectivity for amino acids containing a side chain of high lipophilicity constant, like L-phenylamine, L-tryptophan, L-leucine and L-isoleucine and the effects of stirring speed and temperature on the transport of amino acids through a BLM were studied [18].

In the present work, transport of amino acid through a chloroform bulk liquid membrane containing azo receptors as a carrier was studied. Different experimental conditions, such as the effect of receptor and amino acid concentration in the membrane, the effect of stripping agent, the effect of pH in feed phase, rate of stirring and the effect of time were also investigated. The obtained results are correlated with those acquired by solvent extraction. **Glycine, valine, leucine, and proline** are all amino acids, each with distinct properties. **glycine** has specific receptors (glycine receptors), while **valine, leucine, and proline** are essential for protein synthesis and cellular functions but do not directly bind to receptors. Each amino acid serves distinct roles in biological processes [19]

Herein the present work, selective separation of amino acid through extraction and carrier facilitated transport using chloroform bulk liquid membrane system containing a series of receptors is reported. Valine and leucine were removed from feed phase up to 88.16% by recyclization process. The stripping phase containing amino acids can be used directly

2.1 Methodology

Materials: 1-(Phenyldiazenyl)naphthalene-2-ol (azo dyes), Pyridyl-azo-resorcinol (PAR) were procured from Aldrich. (1, 2-chloro ethoxy ethane), 2,2'-dichloroether were purchased from Aldrich while KOH from Merck. Butanol Chloroform, Benzene methanol were procured from Aldrich. **Glycine, Valine, Leucine, and Proline** were purchased from Merck.

A) Synthesis of receptors/carrier: (J₁-J₂) ;(Scheme I)**Preparation of ionophore J₁;**

In 80 mL of boiling 1-butanol solution of 1-(Phenyldiazenyl)naphthalene-2-ol, 826g (.003mol), KOH .,744g (0.01mol) and bis (1, 2-chloro ethoxy ethane) 1.24 mL (.008mol) were added one by one[20]. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 120°C for 20 h. After this fine precipitates (KCl) formed were filtered off, the solution was evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The residue was taken up in chloroform and washed several times with dilute NaOH and deionized water. The organic phase was separated, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated by distillation under vacuum. (Scheme I)

Dark brown shiny crystals, yield 0.556 g (67.0%), m. p. 120 °C. IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) :3049,2916, 28682 (C-H), 1618 (N=N),1596,1550 (C=C stretch)1266,1253, 1227, 1206 (Ar-O-CH₂),1114, 1020 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 967(aromatic ring).(Figure :2) ¹HNMR(CDCl₃): δ 1.39-1.59(d CH₂)3.45-3.85 (m,4H) (-O-CH₂-O-CH₂),7.48 7.69 (m,aromatic H) (naphthyl C-H) 8.47-8.49(d phenyl H)7.23-8.00(m,aromatic H) (naphthyl C-H).8.47-8.49(d phenyl H), 8.47-8.49(Figur:4) ¹³C NMR spectra : δ 144 (phenyl C-N=N) ,140(naphthyl-C-O) , 77.36,77.0.,76.72 (-O-CH₂- CH₂-O -CH₂- CH₂-O -CH₂- CH₂O -) (Figure:3) LC MS Mass; m/z molecular ion peak (437), 231 (naphthyl ring), 431 (naphthyl ring (-O-CH₂-O-CH₂) M. Wt; (437). (Figure:4)

Structure of receptors (Scheme I and II)

B) Sudan I & PAR were used as such as Ionophore J₃ & J₄ (Scheme II)**C) Synthesis of non-cyclic ionophores (J₅-J₆) (Scheme III)**
Preparation of ionophore J₅; 1,8-bis(2-naphthoxy)-3,6-di-oxaoctane.

In 150 mL of boiling 1-butanol solution 2-naphthol 8.64 g (.06 mol), KOH 3.36 g (0.6 mol) and bis (1, 2-chloro ethoxy ethane) 4.68 mL (.030 mol) were added one by one. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 120°C for 20 h [20]. After this fine precipitates (KCl) formed were filtered off, the solution was evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The residue was taken up in chloroform and washed several times with dilute NaOH and deionized water. The organic phase was separated, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated by distillation under vacuum.

White shiny crystals yield 3.8 g (42.0%), m. p. 80 °C. Elemental analysis: Calculated for (C₂₆H₂₆O₄) M. Wt; (402), C (77.6), H (6.4) Found C (77.5), H(6.5)% . **IR (KBr)** (ν cm⁻¹): 2924, 2872 (C-H), 1253 (Ar-O-CH₂), 1114, 1055 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 967 (aromatic ring). **¹H NMR (CDCl₃)**: δ 3.79 (s, 4H) (-O-CH₂-O-CH₂), 4.45 (t, 2H) (Ar-OCH₂) 7.75(m,7H) (naphthyl C-H). **FAB Mass; m/z molecular ion peak** (402) Calculated for C₂₆H₂₆O₄ M. Wt; (402).

Ionophore J₆; 1,5-bis(2-naphthoxy)-3-oxapentane: White crystalline solid, yield 2.5 g (33.4 %), m. p. 132 °C. **IR (KBr)** (ν cm⁻¹) : 3050,2949 (C-H), 1260(Ar-O -CH₂) 1184,1080,1056(CH₂-O-CH₂) 968(naphthyl C- H). **¹H NMR(CDCl₃)**: 3.58 (s, 4H) (-O-CH₂-O-CH₂), 4.12 (t, 2H) (Ar-O-CH₂) 7.3 (m, 7H) (Aromatic C-H) **Elemental Analysis**: Calculated for (C₂₄H₂₂O₃) M. Wt; (358), C (80.4), H (6.1). Found C (80.3), H (6.3)%

Scheme III n = 3 (J₅) n = 2 (J₆)

2.2 Methods Liquid-liquid extraction

2.2 Extraction studies: In the liquid-liquid extraction studies [21], 10 mL of amino acid solution was vigorously stirred with 10 mL of receptor solution (chloroform) in a 50 mL beaker using magnetic stirrer, the beaker was covered. The amount of amino acid in aqueous phase was initially determined. After 4 h of stirring the mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes for the separation of two phases. The depleted aqueous solution was removed and analyzed for amino acid content [22] by UV-visible spectrophotometer (Lambda 55 Perkin Elmer).

3. BLM Model for Transport Studies.: Transport studies [23] were performed in a “U” tube glass cell at 25 °C. 15 mL of chloroform containing 1.0 x 10⁻³ M of receptor was taken as membrane phase. The source phase was composed of 10 mL of 1.0 x 10⁻¹ M of aqueous amino acid in one limb of the “U” tube and 10 mL of double distilled water served as the receiving phase in the other limb. The membrane phase was constantly stirred for 4 h.

The BLM apparatus (U-type) used for the study is shown in Figure 2. The inner dimension of the transport cell was 70 mm diameter × 250 mm depth. Experiments were carried out at ambient temperature (25 ± 0.5 °C), and the aqueous source (feed) phase (10 mL) amino acid and strip phase (10 mL) deionised water were taken in the BLM apparatus. The chloroform solution (25 mL) contained supramolecular receptors. The organic layer was stirred by Teflon coated magnetic bar (2.0 cm) (DuPont, Haryana, India), both aqueous layers (feed and strip) were stirred using the stirrer. In transport, experiment samples were taken out from the feed and strip phases, and amino acid concentration was measured using spectrophotometer (λ_{max} = 575 nm) with good reproducibility

Figure.5: Schematic experimental setup for bulk liquid membrane for transport of amino acid from chloroform membrane.

Amino acid estimation

The 0.5 mL aqueous amino acid (0.1M) was taken in 10 mL standard flask and the 0.2 mL ninhydrin solution (0.5%) was added and kept in the boiling water for 10 min. Thereafter, 6 mL of 60% ethanol was added with double distilled water until the total volume was 10 mL. In this way calibration curve was plotted ranging from 1.0×10^{-5} M to 1.0×10^{-1} M at $\lambda_{\text{ax}} 575$ nm[24]

4. Results and Discussion:

All measurements were performed in triplicate to check reproducibility. Blank experiments were performed for the extraction and transport study of amino acid in which membrane was devoid of receptor. No detectable transport of amino acid through the liquid membrane was found, suggesting that the transport of amino acid through the liquid membrane was fulfilled by the receptor.

4.1 Effect of receptor and amino acid concentration

To find out the optimum concentration of amino acid for transport and extraction studies, concentration of amino acid was varied from 1×10^{-2} M to 1M at constant receptor concentration (1.0×10^{-4} M). The optimum concentration of amino acid is 1×10^{-1} M for optimization of the receptor, the concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-4} M to 1.0×10^{-2} M at constant amino acid concentration (1×10^{-1} M). The optimum concentration for receptor was found to be 1.0×10^{-4} M (Table 1).

Table 1: Amount of Amino acids extracted into organic phase after 4 h with receptors (J_1 - J_2) in chloroform.

Source phase: 10 mL Amino acid solution

Receptor concentration = 1.0×10^{-4} M (J_1 - J_6) in 15 mL chloroform

Concentration of amino acid	Receptor J_1		Receptor J_2	
	Amount of amino acid extracted= 1.0×10^{-3} M	Distribution ration D_m	Amount of amino acid extracted 1.0×10^{-3} M	Distribution ration D_m
Glycine				
1M	.023	1.008	.011	.0984
1×10^{-1} M)	.036	1.014	.127	1.061
1×10^{-2} M)	.011	1.004	.012	.0992

1 X x10 ⁻³ M)	.14	1.113	.19	1.134
Valin				
1M	.057	1.023	.060	1.011
1 X x10⁻¹ M)	.813	1.580	.617	2.743
1 X x10 ⁻² M)	.012	.0943	.044	1.008
1 X x10 ⁻³ M)	.176	.5285	.182	.583
Lucine				
1M	.055	1.022	.083	1.023
1 X x10⁻¹ M)	.732	1.444	.512	2.032
1 X x10 ⁻² M)	.373	1.120	.069	1.018
1 X x10 ⁻³ M)	.14	.3249	.12	.2435
Prolein				
1M	.057	1.534	.145	1.834
1 X x10 ⁻¹ M)	.217	1.41	.185	2.681
1 X x10 ⁻² M)	.034	1.014	.034	1.014
1 X x10 ⁻³ M)	.023	.5467	.011	.1236

Table 2: Concentration variation of amino acids : Amount of Amino acids extracted in Liquid-liquid extraction studies in 4 hours

Source phase: 10 mL Amino acid solution

Receptor concentration = 1.0 x10⁻³ M (J₁-J₆) in 15 mL chloroform

amino acid Concentration variation	J ₁ Receptor		J ₂ Receptor		J ₅ Receptor		J ₆ Receptor	
	M/L	%	M/L	%	M/L	%	M/L	%
Glycine								
1M	.023	23%	.011	01	-	-	-	-
1 X 10⁻¹ M)	.036	36%	.127	12	.101	10	.101	10
1 X 10 ⁻² M)	.011	11%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Valin								
1M	.057	57%	.060	06	.060	06	.060	06
1 X 10⁻¹ M)	.813	81%	.617	61	.025	02	.025	02
1 X 10 ⁻² M)	.012	12%	.044	04	-	-	-	-

Leucine								
1M	.055	5%	.83	83	.083		.083	08
1 X 10 ⁻¹ M)	.732	73%	.512	51	.029		-	--
1 X 10 ⁻² M)	.373	37%	-	-			-	-

Table 3: Amount of Amino acids transported through chloroform bulk liquid membrane after 24 hours.

Receptor Conc. (J₁-J₆) : = 1.0 x10⁻³ M (J₁-J₆)

Source Phase = Amino acid conc.= 1.0 x10⁻¹ M

Receiving Phase = Deionised water

Concentration of amino acid	Receptor J ₁		Receptor J ₂		Receptor J ₃		Receptor J ₄		Receptor J ₅		Receptor J ₆	
Amount of amino acid transported = 1.0 x10 ⁻³ M/100 mL												
		%		%						%		%
Glycine	.160	16	.120	12	-	-	-	-	.324	32	.354	35
Valin	.260	26	.240	24	-	-	-	-	.88	88	.698	69
Leucine	.011	01	.023	02	.01	-	-	-	.620	62	.523	52
Prolein	.023	02	.06		-	-	-	-	.025	02	.012	

Figure: comparing transport of valine and leucine by receptors

4.2 Effect of solvent

The solvent variation were performed by using dichloromethane, trichloromethane and tetrachlormethane but optimum transport of amino acid were observed in tricholoromethane [25]

4.3 Effect of acid base and salt

Effect of acid base and salt were studied on transport of amino acid and as aminoacid in the zwitter ion form in solution [26].

4.4 Effect of stirring speed

The transport experiments were performed at six different stirring speeds, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 rpm. The optimum speed was found is 400rpm.

4.5 Effect of temperature

As chloroform is nonpolar solvent and has boiling point at low temperature therefore all the transport experiments were performed on room temperature at 298K.

4.6 Effect of time,

The effect of time is studies for the transport of amino acids. At different time interval, 4,8 12,18,24, 36, 48 and 72 hours. The optimum time was found 24 Hours was observed for the Bulk Liquid Membrane transport [27].

5. Conclusion

The results reveals that receptor J₁ & J₂ extracts valin at greater extant and receptor J₅ and J₆ transport valine and leucine at greater extent. The observed trend for the extraction of amino acids by these receptors is valin>leucine>glycine (Table 1). Structure of receptor affected the extraction and transport phenomena. Receptors J₁, J₂ possess tri and diethylene glycol chain length with rigid naphthyl end groups. It is suggested that receptors (J₁-J₂) interact with amino acids by hydrogen bonding between -NH₄⁺ moiety of amino acid and donor oxygen sites of the receptor. This series of azoreceptors with naphthyl end groups present π -stacking interactions that enhances the extractability of the receptor compared to simple glycols as reported earlier [28]

The extraction of amino acids observed to follow the sequence of hydrophobicity scale i.e. valine>Lucine >glycine. Glycine displays less extraction due to its hydrophilic character in comparison to other amino acids.

The efficiency of the BLM model depends on the important parameters such as the pH of the feed, amino acid concentration, carrier concentration, stirring speed and temperature[29].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Madhyapradesh Council of Science and Technology (MPCST) Bhopal, India for financial assistance for the project no. 1082/CST/R&D/2012 and support of SAIF Punjab for spectral analysis is also acknowledged.

References:

- [1] Danesi, P.(1984). A simplified model for the coupled transport of metal ions through hollow fiber supported liquid membranes .J. Memb. Sci. 20: 231–248.
- [2] Koreyta, J(1982). Ions Electrodes and Membranes, pp. 137–141. Wiley, New York
- [3] Aridbod, F., Ganjali, M.R., Dinarvand, R., Norouz, P.,(2008). Developments in the field of conducting and non-conducting polymer based potentiometric membrane sensors for ions over the past decade. Sensors. 8, 2331–2341.
- [4] Petrovic, T.T., Jonsson, J.A. (2002). Application of SLM extraction of investigation of metal–humic acid bindings. Desalination. 148, 247-254
- [5] Kocherginsky, N.M., Qian, Y. and Seelam, L. (2007). Recent advances in supported liquid membrane technology. Sep. Purif. Technol. 53, 171–177.
- [6] Kocherginsky, N.M. and Qian, Y., (2007). Big carousel mechanism of copper removal from ammoniacal wastewater through supported liquid membrane. Sep. Purif. Technol. 54, 104–116 (2007)
- [7] Yang, Q., Kocherginsky, N.M. (2006) Copper recovery and spent ammoniacal etchant regeneration based on hollow fiber supported liquid membrane technology: from bench-scale to pilot-scale tests. J. Memb. Sci. 286, 301–309
- [8] Mutihac, L., Buschmann, H.-J., Diacu, E. (2002). Calixarene derivatives as carriers in liquid membrane separation. Desalination. 148, 253–256.
- [9] Izatt, R., Clark, G.A., Bradshaw, J.S., Lamb, J.D., Christansen, J.J(1986). Macrocycle-facilitated transport of ions in liquid membrane systems. J. Sep. Purif. Methods 15, 21-24
- [10] Tummler, B., Maass, G., Vogtle, F., Weber, E. (1979). Open chain polyethers: influence of aromatic donor end groups on thermodynamics and kinetics of alkali metal ion complex formation. J. Am. Chem. Soc. 101, 2588–2599 (1979)

- [11] Nakamura, H., Nishida, H., Takagi, M., Ueno, K. (1982). Chromogenic crown ethers reagents for spectrophotometric determination of sodium and potassium. *Anal. Chem. Acta* 139, 219–227.
- [12] Tomar, J., Bhatanagar, M., Sharma, U. (2007) Isolation and characterization of complexes of alkali and alkaline earth metal cations with synthetic podands. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 76, 1–4.
- [13] Awasthy, A., Bhatanagar, M., Tomar, J., and Sharma, U., (2006). Design and synthesis of redox switched lariat ethers and their application for transport of alkali and alkaline earth metal cations across supported liquid membrane, *J. Bioinorg. Chem. Appl.*, article ID 97141, 1-4.
- [14] Singh, R., Mehta, R., Kumar, V. (2011)., Simultaneous removal of copper, nickel and zinc metal ions using bulk liquid membrane system. *Desalination.* 272, 170–173
- [15] Tomar, J., Sharma, U. (2006). Design and Synthesis of azobenzene bridged photoresponsive ionophores and their application in extraction and liquid membrane transport of main group metal ions. *J. Main Group Metal Chem.* 29(3), 119–126
- [16] M. Ma, D. He, Q. Wang and Q. Xie, (2001). Kinetics of europium III transport through a liquid membrane containing HEH (EHP) in kerosene, *Talanta* 55, 1109–1117.
- [17] Chen J, Hooley RJ, Zhong W (2022). Applications of Synthetic Receptors in Bio-analysis and Drug Transport. *Bioconjug Chem.* 21,3(12),2245-2253.
- [18] Demirtas, H.N., Bozkurt, S., Durmaz, M., Yilmaz, M., Sirit, A. (2009). Chiral calix[4]azacrowns for enantiometric recognition of amino acid derivatives. *Tetrahedron.* 65(15), 3014–3018.
- [19] Kim, L., Hamdi, A., Stancu, A.D. (2010).. Selective membrane transport of amino acids by functionalised calix[4]arenes. *J Incl Phenom Macrocycl Chem* 66, 55–59.
- [20] Eyal, A. M. and Bresseler, E., (1993). Mini-Review Industrial Separation of Carboxylic and Amino Acids by Liquid Membrane: Applicability, Process Consideration, and Potential Advantages”, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, 41, 287
- [21] Imdad S. and Dohare R.K.(2022):A critical review on heavy metals removal using ionic liquid membranes from the industrial wastewater. *Chemical Engineering and Processing-Process.* 173,1-13.
- [22] Itoh, H., Thien, M. P., Hatton, T. A. and Wang, D. I. C., (1990). Water Transport Mechanism in Liquid Emulsion Membrane Process for the Separation of Amino Acids, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 51, 309.
- [23] Moore, S. (1968)., Amino Acid Analysis, Aqueous Dimethyl Sulfoxide as Solvent for the Ninhydrin Reaction”, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 243, 6281.
- [24] Renon, H., Deblay, P. and Minier, M., (1990). Separation of L-valine from Fermentation Broths Using a Supported Liquid Membrane, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, 35, 123 (1990).
- [25] Moraga-Cid, G., Aguayo, L.G. (2021). Glycine Receptors. In: Offermanns, S., Rosenthal, W. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Molecular Pharmacology*. Springer, Cham.
- [26] Tomar, J., Awasthy, A., Sharma, U. 109 (2008). Synthetic ionophores for separation of Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ & Mg²⁺ metal ions using liquid membrane technology. *Desalination* 232, 102–109.
- [27] Tomar, J., Chauhan, P.S. & Sharma, U., (2017). Isolation and Characterization of Host Guest Complexes through Spectroscopy and Liquid–Liquid Extraction Studies. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 9(9), 37-43.
- [28] Tomar, J., Chauhan, P.S. & Sharma, U. (2012). Selective transport of zinc and copper ions by synthetic ionophores using liquid membrane technology. *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.* 74, 99–107.
- [29] Raizada. P., Tomar, J., & Sharma, U., 2011. Design and synthesis of series of receptors and their use in extraction and liquid membrane transport studies of amino acid. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 88, 505-511.